

1.62, 66.7%). R_{Rt} of sterol acetates were given relative to cholesterol.

The interesting observations reported earlier that alkanols⁸ possess anti-inflammatory activity comparable with β -methasone and β -sitosterol⁹ possesses anti-inflammatory activity, similar to hydrocortisone and oxyphenbutazone and antipyretic activity similar to acetyl salicylic acid, suggest that the presence of sterols and alkanols in the leaves of this plant might be responsible for its medicinal value.

Tlc (silica gel) plates were developed with carbon tetrachloride-ethyl acetate (95 : 5) for determining R_f values, whereas argentation tlc plates (silica gel-20% silver nitrate) were developed five times with methylene chloride-carbon tetrachloride (1 : 5, v/v) for separation of acetyl derivatives of sterols.

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Spectrophotometric Studies on Bisulphite-salicyldehyde Compound

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THE addition compound between carbonyl group and bisulphite ion has an importance since it is a basis for the determination of many aldehydes and ketones¹. A series of aldehyde-bisulphite compounds have been studied and their dissociation

constants were determined by Keip and Bauer². Regarding spectrophotometric studies, a furfural-bisulphite complex have been described earlier³.

The present method may be used for the estimation of microgram quantities of bisulphite ion. The spectrophotometric studies can also be used to obtain quantitative information of aldehyde-sulphite equilibria.

Experimental

A 0.095 M stock solution of salicyldehyde (B.D.H., England) in ethanol-water (40%, v/v) was used. A 0.0034 M sulphite solution was prepared by dissolving reagent grade Na₂S₂O₃ (E. Merck, G.R.) in double-distilled water. All other chemicals used were reagent grade. All aqueous solutions were made by using double-distilled water.

Absorbance measurements were made on a Beckman 26 double beam uv-visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm quartz cells. A Systonics 331 expanded scale pH meter equipped with glass electrode was used for pH measurements.

Procedure for the determination of sulphite: To an aliquot (0.5-2.0 ml) of the salicyldehyde solution (9.54×10^{-4} M) were added various amounts (0.5-6.0 ml) of a solution containing 50.0 to 550.0 μ g sulphite. pH of the solution was adjusted between 3.5 to 6.0 followed by addition of sodium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (1.0 ml). The volume of the resulting mixture was brought up to the mark in a 10 ml volumetric flask. The absorbance was measured at 256 nm after 30 min against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance spectra: The absorbance value of salicyldehyde was found to decrease due to the formation of a complex with bisulphite ion. Fig. 1 shows typical absorption curves ($\lambda_{max} = 256$ nm) for salicyldehyde and bisulphite-salicyldehyde complex.

Working range: The absorbance values of several salicyldehyde solutions containing known amounts of sulphite were taken. In all cases, blanks were used as references. It was found that the absorbance values gradually decreased with the addition of sulphite. It is seen from Fig. 2 that such a decrease occurs linearly upto 55.0 ppm sulphite, and further addition of sulphite causes deviation from linearity. Thus, the working range for the determination of sulphite by using salicyldehyde has been found to be upto 55.0 ppm with the detection limit⁴ of 2.4 ppm.

Effect of pH and diverse ions: The absorbance values of solutions were sensitive to pH. Below pH 3.5, no appreciable⁴ absorbance difference between bisulphite ion and salicyldehyde was detectable. Above this pH, with the formation of higher amounts of bisulphite-salicyldehyde complex, the absorbance difference ($\bar{D}$) remained the same until

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Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra: (I) salicyldehyde solution only; in presence of (II) 20.5, (III) 44.0, (IV) 88.0 and (V) 147.0 ppm sulphite.

The tolerance limits of diverse ions (within an error of $\pm 2\%$) were studied. The results indicated that for determination of 27.6 ppm sulphite, no interference was caused by 500 ppm of chloride (as NaCl), nitrate (as NaNO_3), sulphate (as Na_2SO_4); 200 ppm of fluoride (as NaF), tartarate (as Na-K-tartarate), EDTA (as Na-EDTA); 100 ppm of Mn^{II} (as MnSO_4), Cd^{II} (as CdSO_4), Zn^{II} (as Zn-acetate). Fe^{III} , iodide, thiosulphate and thiocyanate ions have been found to interfere.

Nature of the compound: The Job's method of continuous variations⁶ was applied by mixing varying proportions of equimolar solutions of salicyldehyde and sulphite. The difference ($\bar{D}$) between the absorbance of each mixture and the value which would have been obtained had no reaction with bisulphite occurred, was calculated. This was plotted against the ratio (R) of the sulphite concentration to the total concentration of sulphite and salicyldehyde. A representative result for solutions with total molarity of $1.18 \times 10^{-4} M$ for sulphite plus salicyldehyde at pH 5 and temperature 34° are shown in Fig. 3. The minimum indicates that a

Fig. 2. Working range: (I) 1.669×10^{-4} , (II) 9.539×10^{-5} , (III) $4.769 \times 10^{-5} M$ salicyldehyde.

pH 6.0 was reached. Above pH 6.0, with the less availability of HSO_3^- , the concentration of the bisulphite-salicyldehyde compound decreased, as a result the absorbance value would again be nearer to pure salicyldehyde solution.

complex containing bisulphite and salicyldehyde is formed in a 1:1 ratio. Job's curve of similar nature can also be formed in some other cases^{7,8}. However, these results show that maximum reaction occurs at equal concentrations of sulphite and

Fig. 3. Job's plot [$\bar{D}$ = absorbance of sulphite salicydehyde mixture - absorbance of salicydehyde solution, R = sulphite concentration/total concentration of sulphite + salicydehyde].

salicydehyde and that the complex is of the following type²,

The addition compound thus formed is an *o*-hydroxy sulphonic acid or its salt which splits to a certain degree into its components in aqueous solution. The formation of such hydroxy compound has also been reported in connection with formaldehyde-bisulphite addition complex⁹. Nevertheless, the extent of this decomposition depends upon the strength of the union between the components (which is a function of the temperature), the concentration and pH of the solution¹.

Molar absorptivity and formation constant : The negative values of $\bar{D}$ for a complex indicate that accurate evaluation of molar absorptivity and formation constant is a tricky one¹⁰. Rose Drago^{11,12} formulated a most generalised equation (equation 1) to determine equilibrium constant spectrophotometrically. This equation (1) contains two unknowns: K and ϵ_c , respectively the equilibrium constant and molar absorptivity of the complex. A straightforward, convenient graphical method, based on the consideration of two linear plots, for solving the Rose-Drago equation has been reported by Seal *et al.*¹³

$$K^{-1} = \frac{C_D^0 C_A^0 (\epsilon_c - \epsilon_A)}{d - d_A^0} - C_D^0 - C_A^0 + \frac{d - d_A^0}{\epsilon_c - \epsilon_A} \quad (1)$$

were, C_D^0 and C_A^0 are the initial concentrations of the donor and acceptor, respectively, ϵ_A is the molar absorptivity of the acceptor, d_A^0 is the absorbance of the initial concentration of the acceptor, and d corresponds to the total absorbance at any given wavelength for a cell of 1 cm path length. Equation (1) can be written in the form :

$$y = A + BC - B^2 x \quad (2)$$

where, $y = \frac{C_D^0 C_A^0}{d - d_A^0}$, $C = C_D^0 + C_A^0$, $x = d - d_A^0$,

$$A = K^{-1} / (\epsilon_c - \epsilon_A) \text{ and } B = 1 / (\epsilon_c - \epsilon_A).$$

Now, x is a linear function of C_D , the equilibrium concentration of the complex and equation (2) gives a linear plot of y vs x with slope, $s = -B^2$ and intercept, $i = A + BC$. Finally, $K = B/A$ and $\epsilon_c = 1/B + \epsilon_A$ may be calculated.

Using the above graphical procedure, the equilibrium constant and molar absorptivity values of salicydehyde-bisulphite system have been calculated. A representative linear plot of y vs x for this system is shown in Fig. 4. The calculated values of ϵ_c and K are respectively $-172 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $5.29 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The negative ϵ_c values for other systems, though not common, have been reported earlier¹⁴. The value of K obtained by the present method is comparable to K values for other aldehyde-sulphite compounds determined previously by other method².

Fig. 4. Plot of y vs x (equation 2).

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Determination of Zinc in Milk Samples using 1-(2-Quinolylazo)-2,4,5-trihydroxybenzene as Spectrophotometric Reagent

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ZINC is an essential metal in biological system and its essentiality for human being was recognised only recently. Zinc has been found considerably in milk samples and in this paper the trace amounts of the metal has been determined spectrophotometrically by 1-(2-quinolylazo)-2,4,5-trihydroxybenzene (QATB)¹. The method is simple and rapid.

Experimental

Synthesis of QATB: Stoichiometric amounts of 2-hydrazinoquinoline² (1.59 g, 0.01 mol, dissolved in the minimum amount of dilute hydrochloric acid) and 2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone³ (1.4 g, 0.01 mol in ethanol) were mixed and refluxed for 30 min. The solution was then cooled and made ammoniacal. Excess of ammonia was boiled off and the solution was allowed to stand overnight. The dark red precipitate obtained was recrystallised from ethanol and dried over phosphorus pentoxide. The purity of the compound was checked by thin layer chromatography and elemental analysis (Found: C, 64.2; H, 3.8; N, 15.1. C₁₅H₁₁N₂O₃ requires: C, 64.05; H, 3.91; N, 14.95%). A 1 × 10⁻³ M reagent solution was prepared. Reagent solutions were discarded when a week old.

Preparation of solutions: A 1 × 10⁻³ M stock solution of zinc was prepared by dissolving appro-

prate amount of analytical grade zinc(II) sulphate heptahydrate in water, standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁴, and further diluted as required for working standards. A fresh 1% solution was prepared and kept in amber-coloured bottle. A 0.5 N NaOH solution was prepared.

Standard calibration curve for zinc: To a suitable aliquot containing zinc (2.8-9.0 μg) were added 1% ascorbic acid (0.5 ml) and 1 × 10⁻³ M QATB (1 ml). A 0.5 N NaOH solution (2.0 ml) was then added and diluted to 10 ml keeping the final concentration of ethanol to 40% (v/v). The absorbance was measured at 560 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Addition of an ethanolic solution of QATB to a very dilute solution of zinc(II), in a medium containing not less than 30% (v/v) ethanol (otherwise a precipitate was obtained), resulted in a dark brown colour in alkaline solution having λ_{max} at 560 nm. The colour intensity was shown maximum and constant at 0.05-0.25 N NaOH, and 25 molar excess of reagent was required for complete complexation. Beer's law validity range with optimum concentration range in ppm is 0.0-1.37 and 0.28-0.9, respectively. Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity are 0.0012 μg Zn/cm² and 5.4 × 10⁴ dm² mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively. The composition (M : L) determined by Job's method is 1 : 2. The method is highly sensitive as well as selective for zinc, and the transition metals either do not form complex with QATB in high alkaline medium or if formed by a few, are masked by cyanide except manganese. In absence of manganese(II), zinc ions which are also masked by cyanide, are demasked by adding formaldehyde solution, and this procedure was applied to find out trace levels of zinc in milk samples.

Effect of foreign ions: Effect of diverse ions on the colour development of zinc complex with QATB was studied by taking 0.65 μg ml⁻¹ of zinc(II), adding varying amounts of diverse ions and following the recommended procedure. It was observed that fluoride, nitrate, nitrite, sulphate, sulphite, alkaline earths, lanthanides, aluminium(III), indium(III), antimony(III), bismuth(III), chromium(III), platinum metals (except palladium) and thorium(IV) did not interfere at all. However, sulphide and manganese(II) interfered seriously. Cyanide also interfered but a 150-fold cyanide concentration is tolerated in presence of 1% formaldehyde solution. This is due to instability of tetracyanozincate ions in presence of formaldehyde⁵ and zinc ions are again free to interact with the reagent. Results of tolerance limits, in parts per million (given in parenthesis) of various ions in solution that caused a deviation smaller than ± 2% in absorbance are as follows: chloride (600), bromide (600), iodide (100), thiosulphate (100), phosphate (50), bromate (20), thiocyanate (40), citrate (40), tartarate (40), oxalate (20), EDTA (25), Fe²⁺ (56, masked by 1%